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LAUDS FACTORIES

Deliverable 2.1 - Map of technical digital and physical factors for transformation

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	Name and Surname	Role in the Project	Partner
Authors	Chia-Yin Lin Dr Robert Mies	Project assistant Senior researcher	TUB
Reviewed by	Dr Fedoua Kasmi	Senior researcher	UL
	Michel Langhammer	Researcher	HSU
Approved by	Dr Julien Colomb	Project manager	TUB

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Executive summary

The deliverable report D2.1 outlines the initial direction for preparing the digital and physical infrastructure required to support LAUDS manufacturing. Building on the expectations identified in the D1.1 report, this deliverable advances the analysis by assessing first the user needs through a targeted survey of 34 open call applicants. The derived findings highlight priority infrastructure needs from the perspective of two key user groups: business users and creators and determine their relative importance. Based on these results, we conducted Quality Function Deployment (QFD) analyses with four project partners acting as LAUDS factories to translate the identified user needs into technical requirements and define corresponding target values. These results were then consolidated into a circular diagram and mind map to visualize the current infrastructure landscape and identify potential gaps. This process provides a structured foundation for identifying technical capacities aligned with stakeholder needs while demonstrating the applicability of the QFD methodology as a systematic quality management tool. It further provides strategic input for the ongoing development of LAUDS factories, supporting their progression towards resilient, inclusive, sustainable, and culturally embedded models for urban manufacturing.

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1. Introduction

This report provides empirical findings to enhance understanding of the transformational infrastructure requirements for LAUDS factories towards facilitating business and creators in the collaborative design and prototyping stage for small-batch manufacturing. Through its analysis, it defines a set of infrastructure requirements that address the diverse needs of those LAUDS Factory projects' main target groups. This contributes towards the establishing of a flexible and shared LAUDS factory model to support the future of open and distributed manufacturing. While this model provides an initial blueprint, it is neither final nor fixed, as LAUDS factories are still in an early phase of development. Rather, it helps projects to refine or adjust requirements based on practical applications, with real-world experience revealing the most essential elements of the methodological framework.

The goal of the deliverable D2.1 report is to identify the digital and physical infrastructure requirements necessary for the transformation of LAUDS factories. This mapping process lays a first pillar for the development of the project's LAUDS factories model for facilitating open and sustainable manufacturing and fostering collaboration across various sectors. This collaboration involves small and medium-sized manufacturing businesses as well as artists, designers and other creative professionals (all being referred to hence forward as creators), working together to promote resource sharing and co-innovation within urban manufacturing environments. Additionally, it is important to ensure that infrastructure planning aligns with the requirements for adaptability, resilience, and sustainability in urban manufacturing, providing effective support for the advancement of the LAUDS factories model. Moreover, the inherent localisation of LAUDS factories means that the infrastructure of each them will be matched with its specific environmental setting and available resources. This requires configurations to optimise resource utilisation from local sources and to support manufacturing models that closely integrate with overall local environmental, economic and social dynamics and foster stronger community connections.

To gather insights for aligning infrastructure capabilities as part of the LAUDS factory model, we analysed user needs based on previous findings from literature and WP1 co-creation workshops (D1.1), and collected survey responses on them from 34 open call applicants, reflecting specific interests of businesses and creators. We then worked closely with four out of seven LAUDS factory project partners to conduct quality function deployment (QFD) analyses translating those user needs into technical requirements. These partners include:

- UNIVERSITE DE LORRAINE (UL) in Nancy, France, operating a university-associated fab living lab platform for green and circular economy innovations with digital machines for a

distributed production and plastic recycling tool chain; acting as a LAUDS factory for OC#1 LAUDS Exploration and OC#2 LAUDS Replication

- FAB CITY HAMBURG EV (FCHH) in Germany, operating from Fab Lab St. Pauli as an umbrella network of makerspaces and companies in the metropolitan area of Hamburg for long-term distributed manufacturing capacity building; acting as a LAUDS factory for OC#1 LAUDS Exploration
- Taller para la Materialización y el Desarrollo de (grandes) Conceptos (TMDC) in Barcelona, Spain, an advanced independent, large-scale co-manufacturing space for digital and conventional machines with small and medium-sized company residents and individual members; acting as a LAUDS factory for OC#2 LAUDS Replication
- BAUHAUS-UNIVERSITÄT WEIMAR (BUW) also in Germany, planning to utilise a hybrid setup of an associated institute's lab for interface design as well as a bio hacking makerspace in Berlin; acting as a LAUDS factory for OC#2 LAUDS Replication

This selection offers a varied set of perspectives from the LAUDS Factories project for defining technical requirements and target values required to address the identified user needs. The challenge is to jointly translate them into actionable technical target specifications and systematically prioritise them.

The remainder of this report is therefore structured into the following subsequent sections:

- Section 2 – Results outlines the key findings related to user needs, infrastructure requirements, and mapping objectives.
- Section 3 – User Needs provides a brief literature review and describes the investigated user needs, the process of deriving associated requirements, and the survey analysis.
- Section 4 – Conclusion reflects the overall outcome.

In addition, the appendices provide supplementary materials, including some background on the QFD methodology (Appendix A), the survey questions and corresponding open-ended responses (Appendices B and C), as well as a box plot analysis of the survey data (Appendix D).

2. Results

This section summarises the results including from a survey on user needs of the project's main target groups and from a subsequent analysis of technical infrastructure requirements. The latter is illustrated by means of a circular link diagram to illustrate the relationship between user needs and their corresponding technical requirements, followed by mind maps that separately depict digital and physical technical requirements along with their target values. The open data is available under Lauds Factories open data (2.0), "D2.1" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15535394>.

These visualisations were developed following the QFD approach, with input from the four LAUDS Factories partners: UL, FCHH, TMDC and BUW. The methodological background of the quality function deployment (QFD) approach is outlined in Appendix A. The QFD is a systematic customer-centric quality methodology that supports the development, design, and implementation of new products and manufacturing processes. Its primary objective is to translate customer needs and expectations into specific design specifications and technical requirements, integrating and prioritising these systematically throughout the product development process. Ultimately, QFD helps organisations deliver high-quality products and processes as part of multi-generational developments that effectively meet customer demands. The method will be utilised to provide a clear overview of needs, evaluating the current implementation status of digital and physical infrastructure, and identifying key infrastructure gaps.

2.1 User needs of businesses and creators

Understanding user needs is essential as a basis for prioritising the creation of new infrastructure capacity in areas that have the greatest impact. To explore this, a survey was conducted with the LAUDS factory project's two main target groups: business users and creators. The consolidated survey results indicate that while these two groups share similar preferences in several areas, on average, they diverge on certain particular priorities: In terms of physical Infrastructure, digital machines, workstation capacity, functional spaces, material supply and sustainability are sought-after across both groups. Digital Infrastructure such as file sharing repositories and communication tools consistently rank as a top priority for all user types. Version control and code collaboration tools are slightly less prioritised, especially by creators; and user management is less relevant for both groups. In direct comparison, business users expectedly place a stronger emphasis on collaborative project development and business-oriented activities, whereas creators focus more on hands-on training and expert advice. A detailed analysis of the survey results will be presented in the subsequent section 3.

The aggregated findings are illustrated in the following user needs assessment table:

User needs			Importance for business users	Importance for creators	Average
↓					
	Cluster	Individual user needs			
Process	Physical infrastructure	Easy-to-use digital machine tools with sufficient variety for prototyping	4	4	4
		Sufficient capacity of workstations	4	4	4
		Functional areas for prototyping, co-creation, and social interaction	4	4	4
		Seamless system and responsible staff for managing materials inventory	4	4	4
		Easy-to-use digital machine tools for recycling and upcycling of materials	4	4	4
	Digital infrastructure	Easy-to-use digital prototyping tools that connect to manufacturing equipment, enabling seamless transition from design to production	4	4	4
		Easy-to-use groupware platforms for asynchronous collaboration and distributed networks	4	3	4
		Instant messaging tool for quick communication and sharing ideas across the LAUDS network	4	4	4
		An efficient daily operation system, including membership, booking systems, and production management	3	3	3
	Supporting offerings	Inclusive trainings, tools and resources for supporting education in machine usage and development on different skill levels	4	5	5
		A diverse expert pool covering a variety of professional areas	4	5	5
		Accessible consultancy services for product development assistance	4	4	4
		Professional support for product commercialization, business model development, and marketing.	4	3	4
		Established funding mechanisms to support project development and growth of member projects	4	3	4

Table 1 User needs assessment table

2.2 Relationships between user needs and technical requirements

Based on the consolidated QFD input provided by the project partners, the circular link diagram (Figure 1) visualises the connections between user needs (depicted as large grey circles on the bottom) and anticipated technical requirements, categorised into physical infrastructure (dark blue) and digital infrastructure (light blue). The colour-coded lines in the diagram represent contributions from the four project partners (see legend on the lower left-hand side), with the thickness of the lines indicating the strength of the relationship between specific user needs and technical requirements. Additionally, the numbers adjacent to each technical requirement reflect the total number of connections, offering quantitative insights into their relative importance.

Figure 1 Circular link diagram crossing user needs and technical requirements

Key Findings

For physical infrastructure, CNC machines and plastic recycling machines, each with six connections, are identified as most critical components, highlighting their importance in prototyping, production, and sustainability efforts. Laser cutters and 3D printers, with five connections each, similarly play a significant role in supporting prototyping and manufacturing workflows.

For digital infrastructure, digital collaboration platforms for collaborative product development (eight connections) and learning platforms and tools (seven connections) emerge as the most essential elements, facilitating communication, coordination, and skill development. Booking systems (seven connections) and instant messaging tools (six connections) further align strongly with user needs, enhancing operational efficiency and communication. Digital prototyping (five connections) is particularly valuable for virtual design and testing processes, reinforcing its role in driving innovation and optimising workflows.

This analysis underscores the alignment between user needs and technical requirements, providing a clear path for prioritising both physical and digital infrastructure improvements within the LAUDS factories.

2.3 Transformation mind maps

For the analysis of target values and mapping visualisation, further inputs were gathered from the four LAUDS factory project partners and integrated as part of the QFD process. All tools, machines, and facilities were classified into 23 categories, including: electronic tools, 3D printers, automation and robotics, functional space, CNC machines, woodworking and plastic working tools, sanding tools, metalworking tools, portable tools, materials, laser cutters, moulding and casting tools, plastic recycling facilities, various specialised equipment¹, textile prototyping tools, booking systems, digital prototyping, digital collaboration platforms, learning materials/platforms, workspace infrastructure, instant messaging services, project documentation, and CCTV/internet infrastructure. Each requirement was further assessed to determine whether it is existing or desired, and classified as either digital or physical to support subsequent analysis.

2.3.1 Physical infrastructure mind map

The physical infrastructure mind map (see Figure 2) presents improvement vectors of tools and equipment that are viewed as critical to supporting prototyping and production activities within

¹ The category of specialised equipment includes tools and facilities such as paint booths, vacuum forming machines, autoclaves, ceramics kilns, clean workbenches, incubators, and PCR machines.

the sampled LAUDS factories. This step categorises the technical requirements for these tools and facilities, offering a first consolidated overview for prioritised improvements as well as addressing shortcomings to enhance overall functionality and sustainability. Extending outward from the technical requirement categories, the target values associated with each requirement are connected. Target values that are already being addressed are represented by grey-filled boxes connected by solid lines, whereas desired target values are indicated by dashed-outline boxes connected by dashed lines. This structure visualises the implementation status and helps identify areas that require further development for each technical requirement and partner.

The consolidated map shows that a focus on certain foundational digital machine tools is consistently present across all four LAUDS factories: CNC machines, 3D printing equipment, and laser cutters appear frequently, suggesting their central role in prototyping and production as mentioned above.

In contrast, physical infrastructure gaps are visible in tool categories with limited implementation of improvements. These include plastic recycling equipment, such as plastic identification systems, shredders, dryers, extruders for recycled filament, and hot presses for biomaterials. Electronic tools are also underrepresented, including oscilloscopes, etching machines, and soldering workstations. This may indicate a limited focus on these tools from the desired capacity to support electronic prototyping and circular economy practices.

Some tools are widely adopted but are still marked by dashed-line target values, indicating areas for further optimisation. For example, although CNC machines are broadly used, performance limitations suggest the need for upgrades. Potential improvements include transitioning from 3-axis to 5-axis milling, for enhancing precision, increasing the working area and supporting the processing of more complex geometries and materials. Furthermore, adding bending machines would further expand demanded manufacturing capabilities.

This analysis of the physical infrastructure mind map provides a structured overview of both existing strengths and outstanding gaps. By identifying areas requiring development or investment, it supports strategic planning to enhance capabilities and align them with goals in prototyping, production, and sustainability integration.

Figure 2 Physical infrastructure mind map

2.3.2 Digital infrastructure mind map

The digital infrastructure mind map (Figure 3) illustrates the envisioned technical requirements by the four sampled LAUDS factories to address needs for digital platforms and tools essential for facilitating virtual prototyping, collaboration and resource management within the LAUDS factories. This visualisation presents consolidated insights into the different categories requiring development and their improvement vectors.

Thereby, the map highlights the common importance of certain platforms and tools across the different LAUDS factory spaces. For instance, digital collaboration platforms are universally connected to all four, emphasising their critical role in enabling project coordination and effective communication. Similarly, learning platforms, booking and access control systems are identified as critical tools that support knowledge sharing, resource scheduling, and operational efficiency.

The analysis identifies specific gaps in digital infrastructure that may hinder the achievement of operational and strategic goals. For example, material management tools are closely linked to sustainability strategies, underscoring the need for resource tracking systems to support circular economy practices such as reuse, remanufacture, and lifecycle assessment. Limited access to digital prototyping software, including integrated CAD/CAM tools, could result in further unmet user needs that constrain virtual design and testing capabilities. Additionally, the absence of advanced simulation and learning platform functionalities, such as immersive technologies (virtual/augmented reality) and video tutorials, limits opportunities for self-learning and workshop training, representing a notable area for further development.

This analysis of the digital infrastructure mind map provides a consolidated overview of both the strengths and areas for improvement in current digital tools within the sampled LAUDS factories. By identifying critical gaps and opportunities for enhancement, the evaluation supports strategic investments in digital infrastructure, ensuring that they align effectively with objectives related to collaboration, prototyping, and sustainability planning and tracking.

Figure 3 Digital infrastructure mind map

2.3.3 Prioritisation of technical requirements (UL example)

To prioritise the importance of technical requirements, the relationship matrix as additional step the QFD process is utilised, using the example of the partner UNIVERSITE DE LORRAINE (UL) (Table 2). The derived user needs (as per section 2.1) are listed on the left, and technical requirements are positioned across the top (input by UL). The fulfilment relationships between user needs and technical requirements are scored from 0 to 9 within the matrix, enabling the calculation of both absolute and relative importance for each technical requirement. This is an indicative result to inform further decision making within the case setting of UL. The method ensures that technical priorities are directly aligned with the most critical user needs, based on their weighted contributions.

The results indicate that an efficient management system, CNC, laser cutter, and 3D printing workstations are the most critical technologies, as they hold the highest weights (17% and 13%) and are highly associated with multiple user needs. For instance, the user needs "easy-to-use digital machine tools," "sufficient capacity of workstations," and "digital prototyping tools that connect to manufacturing equipment" are closely linked to these three types of technologies. These technologies frequently received a score of 9 in the matrix, demonstrating their key role in fulfilling core user needs. However, it is noteworthy that the efficient management system (17%), which has the highest weight, encompasses a broad range of functionalities, including equipment booking, membership management, automatic billing, material tracking, and energy monitoring. This broad scope suggests that further segmentation of the technology may be necessary to ensure it precisely addresses specific user needs. Without such refinement, the system may face challenges in effectively aligning with distinct operational requirements and could eventually lead to overcomplexity.

Furthermore, the matrix shows that certain user needs do not have corresponding technical requirements with a high score of 9, or in some cases, are not linked to any technical requirement at all. For example, "professional support for product commercialization, business development, and marketing" lacks a relevant technical match, indicating that the current technical requirements are more focused on manufacturing and infrastructure development while providing limited support for business and commercialization needs. Similarly, "a diverse expert pool covering a variety of professional areas" and "accessible consultancy services for product development assistance" appear in the list of user needs but do not receive high scores in the technical requirement matrix. This may suggest that these needs are first of all to be addressed through non-technical support, such as management frameworks, education and training, or market outreach. Addressing these gaps would indeed require additional strategies beyond physical and digital infrastructure to provide complementary support for users.

Technical requirements (product) →	Physical & Digital infrastructure													
<p style="text-align: center;">User needs</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↓</p>	Average importance for all users	Implement an efficient management system, e.g. with equipment booking, membership system, automatic billing, material tracking, and energy monitoring (e.g., Fab Manager)	3D printing workstation / equipment for fast and accurate printing and post-processing	CNC machine for fast and accurate 3-axis milling	Laser Cutter with sufficient cutting area, diode and CO2 lasers for cutting and engraving of different material / geometries	Extruder, dryer and hot press for processing of bio-based materials and plastics recycling	Machines and all digital tool have corresponding video usage instructions and/or manuals as well as demand-based tutorials	Corresponding software for each digital machine	Enable instant messaging, video conferencing	Establish critical collaboration tools (e.g., GitLab, NextCloud), see also Interfacer OS.	CAM slicers	Electronic workstation, with soldering irons and components	Portable tools (drill, jigsaw, grinder, tools)	Project documentation
	Easy-to-use digital machine tools with sufficient variety for prototyping	4	3	9	9	9	0	3	9	0	0	0	0	0
Sufficient capacity of workstations	4	9	9	9	9	9	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Functional areas for prototyping, co-creation, and social interaction	4	0	9	9	9	0	0	3	0	3	0	9	9	0
Seamless system and responsible staff for managing materials inventory	4	9	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Easy-to-use digital machine tools for recycling and upcycling of materials	4	9	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Easy-to-use digital prototyping tools that connect to manufacturing equipment, enabling seamless transition from design to production	4	3	9	9	9	1	9	9	0	0	9	0	0	0
Easy-to-use groupware platforms for asynchronous collaboration and distributed networks	4	3	0	0	0	0	9	1	3	9	0	0	0	3
Instant messaging tool for quick communication and sharing ideas across the LAUDS network	4	9	0	0	0	0	9	0	9	0	0	0	0	0
An efficient daily operation system, including membership, booking systems, and production management	3	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Inclusive trainings, tools and resources for supporting education in machine usage and development on different skill levels	5	9	9	9	9	9	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
A diverse expert pool covering a variety of professional areas	5	3	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	0	0	0	0	0
Accessible consultancy services for product development assistance	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Professional support for product commercialization, business model development, and marketing	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Established funding mechanisms to support development and growth of member projects	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Absolute importance (sum of products of average importance and relationship score)</i>		260	198	198	198	166	156	105	65	48	36	36	36	11
Relative importance in % (total share)		17	13	13	13	11	10	7	4	3	2	2	2	1

Table 2 Prioritisation of technical requirements (UL example)

3. User needs survey

This section explains how we identified and structured user needs. Following a brief literature review for positioning the work, deriving of user needs from the results of D1.1 “Results and lessons learned of co-creative workshops” report, we mapped out the key functionalities required to effectively reflect user needs. As mentioned above, the user needs form an important input to systematically develop the QFD analysis.

3.1 Literature review

In the context of Industry 4.0, the integration of digital and physical infrastructure components has become a crucial focus for transforming the manufacturing industry. Lee, Bagheri, and Kao (2015) introduce a cyber-physical systems (CPS) architecture that emphasises the importance of automation and real-time data processing in optimising manufacturing processes, laying advanced groundwork for the concept of the smart factory. As CPS continues to enhance industrial connectivity and data analysis, fab labs and makerspaces have been working towards democratising increasingly accessible manufacturing technology for decades, enabling individuals and small groups to share resources and engage in personalised bottom-up innovation (Fiaidhi & Mohammed, 2018). With the rise of the maker movement, the role of makerspaces as urban manufacturing spaces emerged gradually, representing a model of decentralised, locally focused production that aligns with global sustainability goals. Hennelly et al. (2019) explore whether community-based makerspaces could become scalable models of redistributed manufacturing (RDM). They find that makerspaces still play a limited role in local production systems and that the literature lacks in-depth examination of their evolution and contribution towards (urban) manufacturing. Currently, most makerspaces focus on education and hobbies, with limited examples of local manufacturing readiness, indicating that more support is needed to transition makerspaces towards production applications. Accessible data centricity and integration as in CPS-enabled manufacturing architectures is yet even to be broadly modelled and established for open and distributed manufacturing, leading towards a larger scope once again.

In response, the LAUDS Factory project aims to create a more accessible and data-centric open innovation model to facilitate the transition of existing makerspace infrastructures into open collaborative and distributed design and manufacturing models. To support this transition in terms of access to infrastructure, the *Internet of Production Alliance* (IOP) makes an interesting contribution with its *Open-Know-Where Initiative* providing a global map and integrated database of makerspace facilities and machinery that is openly accessible (Internet of Production Alliance: <https://map.internetofproduction.org/>). This platform promotes knowledge democratisation and supports distributed manufacturing practices, offering LAUDS factories critical data to align with

global standards and best practices. Similarly, the *Fab Lab Inventory*, a detailed resource listing of essential tools such as laser cutters, CNC milling machines, and 3D printers (Fab Foundation: <https://fabfoundation.org/getting-started>), serves as a foundational reference for establishing multifunctional makerspaces for producing “almost anything”. By leveraging these resources, civil society and educational objectives are fostered to drive social innovation and sustainability goals in urban manufacturing.

The open source hardware (OSH) concept covers yet another potential innovation mode for creating technical collective knowledge through openness and accessibility instead of protecting and appropriating it exclusively. However, according to previous research by Mies, Bonvoisin, and Stark (2019), despite the OSH idea’s growing popularity as an alternative model for intellectual property management, its practices remain fragmented and diverse. This research found that current groupware solutions generally lack comprehensive public/private synchronous/asynchronous communication channels, requirements management functions, and data federation capabilities, which limits the collaborative potential of open source product development (Mies, Bonvoisin, & Stark, 2019). The findings provide some guidance for the infrastructure needs of LAUDS factories, especially in facilitating cross-organisational knowledge sharing and collaborative communication.

Furthermore, Rieken et al. (2024) highlighted that some companies are utilising corporate makerspaces (CMS) to foster employee co-creation and cross-disciplinary collaboration. This culture of innovation not only stimulates creativity but also creates new opportunities for corporate development (Rieken, Heck, Heinzen, & Meboldt, 2024). Although the target groups, overall goals and environmental setting of these efforts are completely different, this mission shares some similarities to LAUDS factories in terms of the overall direction of the associated technical scope and activities.

In response to these developments, the LAUDS Factories project aims to address opportunities and gaps by bringing together entrepreneurs and artists as per the New European Bauhaus (NEB) framework. By facilitating collaboration among these very different target groups, the transfer of artistic experimental knowledge, and the sharing of expertise in manufacturing process development based on OSH principles, the project seeks to drive sustainable and distributed product innovation and realise the potential for community-based innovation in urban manufacturing. This deliverable therefore maps associated sets of physical and digital infrastructure requirements and KPIs. This work aims to form the basis for the development of an integrated LAUDS factory model which will serve as a paradigm for cross-disciplinary open innovation on sustainable manufacturing practices, promoting a diverse set of infrastructure offerings for community-driven, open and distributed manufacturing.

3.2 Derivation of user needs

Through a user needs survey targeting applicants for the open call #1 LAUDS Exploration, which funds and supports SMEs and creatives in joint projects for sustainable urban transitions, we yielded 34 responses, offering insights into how target groups prioritise various tools, infrastructure, and facilities. Building on results from D1.1 Report "Results and lessons learnt of co-creative workshops" (see Figure 4)², we identified possible overall digital or physical infrastructure and supporting offerings required to meet the therein elicited needs. We categorised all collected elements and ultimately identified 11 key areas for better overview (see the first two columns in Table 3). Subsequent discussions with the four Lauds Factory project partners refined these 11 areas, resulting in suitable functional descriptions of user needs. These descriptions are presented in the third column of Table 3 as part of the user needs analysis. For instance, to establish a "network of designers and production facilities," collaboration platforms, sufficient digital and physical production facilities, and meeting or workshop spaces may be necessary to support prototyping, manufacturing, and networking activities. We therefore systematically conceptualised the technologies and facilities needed for each user need identified in Figure 4 and crossed it with literature to articulate survey items listed in appendix B.

UNIVERSITÉ DE LORRAINE	maker			
Network of designers and production facilities	Physical space	Raw materials	Innovation Labs	Space
consultancy desk	Accessible location for learning and drafting production plans	Technology/Machines	Facilities	Business model
Networking	Expertise	Human resources	Support for project leaders	Membership subscriptions
	Funding	Marketing and sales	Municipal support for premises	Expert availability
		Infrastructure	Feedback mechanism, flexible production cells, expert availability	Value-chain for sorting and repairing
		Space	Change in value perception, competitive advantages for local products	Material library
		Specific Machinery	Value-chain for sorting and repairing	Visual link tree
		Urban Transformation	Material library	

Figure 4 Elicited user needs from D1.1 report

² See URL: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135986/results>.

Category	Key area	User needs
Physical infrastructure	Physical prototyping tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy-to-use digital machine tools with sufficient variety for prototyping
	Space/workplace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sufficient capacity of workstations • Functional areas for prototyping, co-creation, and social interaction
Digital infrastructure	Digital prototyping tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy-to-use digital prototyping tools that connect to manufacturing equipment, enabling seamless transition from design to production
	Collaboration digital tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy-to-use groupware platforms for asynchronous collaboration and distributed networks
	Digital learning resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive training, tools and resources for supporting education in machine usage and development on different skill levels
	Online community tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instant messaging tool for quick communication and sharing ideas across the LAUDS network
	Operation management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An efficient daily operation system, including membership, booking systems, and production management
	Materials management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless system and responsible staff for managing materials inventory • Easy-to-use digital machine tools for recycling and upcycling of materials
Supporting offerings	Funding support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established funding mechanisms to support project development and growth of member projects
	Expert/knowledge/consulting support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A diverse expert pool covering a variety of professional areas • Accessible consultancy services for product development assistance
	Business/marketing strategy support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional support for product commercialisation, business model development, and marketing.

Table 3 User needs by key infrastructure areas

3.3 Survey analysis

This survey investigated emergent user needs of LAUDS factories. The goal was to identify how respondents prioritise various elements, such as facilitation activities, prototyping infrastructure, collaboration community facilities, digital communication and collaboration tools, and environmental sustainability measures (see appendix B "Survey questions for data acquisition"). Additionally, insights from individual users were gathered through open-ended questions (see appendix C "Responses to open-ended survey questions"). The 34 respondents were categorised

into three distinct groups for analysis. The first group, business, comprised 16 respondents who identified themselves as 'SME' or 'start-up,' regardless of their specific roles. The second group, creators, included 11 respondents who identified as 'artist' or 'designer' but did not associate themselves with 'SME' or 'start-up.' The third group, others, consisted of 7 respondents who did not identify with any of the aforementioned categories. This group included a diverse range of participants, such as researchers, students, engineers, hobbyists, and even beekeepers.

The following subsections discuss the mean average and median values of the survey responses by the three groups together and separately. For further details, see appendix D “Box Plot Analysis of Survey Data”. The exported survey results are available under Lauds Factories open data (2.0), "D2.1" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15535394>..

3.3.1 Findings on facilitation activities

Respondents rated how helpful they believe the following LAUDS Factory activities would be on a scale from 1 to 6, with 1 being "strongly disagree" and 6 being "strongly agree."

Table 4 Facilitation activities preferences by user type [mean average / median values]

User type	LAUDS Factory introduction event	Technical training	Business model development seminars	Workshops and creative activities	Guided collaborative project development activities
Business	4.81 / 5	4.69 / 5	5.31 / 6	5.38 / 6	5.31 / 5.5
Creator	5.18 / 5	5.55 / 6	4.36 / 4	5.64 / 6	5.45 / 6
Others	5.14 / 5	5.43 / 6	5.29 / 6	5.43 / 6	5.14 / 5
<u>All</u>	<u>5.00 / 5</u>	<u>5.12 / 5</u>	<u>5.00 / 5</u>	<u>5.47 / 6</u>	<u>5.32 / 5</u>

Table 4 shows that both business users and creators gave their highest ratings to workshops & creative activities, scoring 5.38 (mean) / 6 (median) and 5.64 (mean) / 6 (median), respectively. This indicates a shared appreciation for activities that foster creativity and collaboration. Business users also demonstrated a strong preference for business model development seminars, with a mean score of 5.31 and a median of 6, reflecting their interest in project development and business-focused events. Creators placed significant importance on technical training, scoring 5.55 (mean) / 6 (median), emphasizing their preference for hands-on, skill-building opportunities. Other respondents exhibited balanced preferences across all activities, with both mean and median values consistently above 5, reflecting general satisfaction with the proposed offerings.

Overall, most activities received mean and median values exceeding 5, highlighting positive feedback from all user types.

Feedback from the open-ended questions (see Appendix C) further supports these findings. Business users suggested the inclusion of activities such as local creator presentations, mentorship programs, and networking events to support project development. Creators expressed interest in innovation-related topics, including AI, robotics, and the circular economy, as well as personalised training sessions and events led by diverse groups. Other respondents emphasised the importance of technical training and fostering community collaboration to enhance their overall LAUDS factory experience.

3.3.2 Findings on prototyping infrastructure

To assess user preferences for prototyping tools and equipment, respondents rated the frequency of using these facilities in the future on a scale from 1 “never” to 6 “very frequently”.

Table 5 Prototyping tools and equipment preferences by user type [mean average / median values]

User type	3D printer	Laser cutter	CNC machine	Welding equipment	Electronics workstation	Woodworking tools
Business	4.56 / 5	4.19 / 4	4.44 / 4	3.69	3.31 / 3	3.38 / 3.5
Creator	4.64 / 4	4.36 / 4	4.64 / 5	3.82	3.09 / 3	4.36 / 4
Others	4.57 / 5	4.71 / 5	4.43 / 5	4.00	4.14 / 4	4.14 / 4
All	<u>4.59 / 5</u>	<u>4.35 / 4</u>	<u>4.50 / 5</u>	<u>3.79 / 4</u>	<u>3.41 / 3.5</u>	<u>3.85 / 4</u>

Overall, the survey results indicate that 3D printers and CNC machines are in the highest demand, with average ratings consistently above 4.5 across user groups. Laser cutters also received favourable ratings, though with more variation between user types. In contrast, welding equipment, electronics workstations, and woodworking tools were less prioritized, with mean average /median ratings generally below 4, indicating lower overall demand.

Additional facility requirements:

Feedback from open-ended questions provided additional insights into specific equipment requirements. Business users highlighted the need for specialised tools, including a press for creating recycled plastic plates and equipment such as a heat press, grinder, and stove for bio-based board production. They also expressed a need for tools to support work with ceramic materials, emphasising their focus on material-specific applications. Creators underscored the

importance of having electronics prototyping areas, woodworking benches equipped with clamping devices, and equipment for textile-related projects, such as sewing machines and materials for various printing techniques, including silk screen, etching, and linocut. In contrast, other respondents did not provide substantial additional feedback, suggesting their equipment needs align more closely with the tools already outlined in the survey.

Given the LAUDS Factories project’s focus on sustainability, the heat press machine, which was mentioned twice in the feedback, was incorporated into the final technical requirements. This addition aims to support recycling and sustainable practices, ensuring alignment with the project’s overarching goals.

3.3.3 Findings on collaboration and community facilities

To assess user preferences for collaboration and community spaces, respondents rated the importance of various facilities for project development and collaboration on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree):

Table 6 Collaboration and community facilities preferences by user type [mean average / median values]

User type	Meeting/brains forming room	Open workspace	Coffee area	Event space	Project display area
Business	5.06 / 5	5.13 / 5	5.06 / 5	4.81 / 5	5.25 / 5.5
Creator	5.18 / 5	5.27 / 5	4.82 / 5	5.18 / 5	5.18 / 5
Others	4.57 / 5	4.57 / 5	5.43 / 6	4.43 / 5	4.57 / 5
All	<u>5.00 / 5</u>	<u>5.06 / 5</u>	<u>5.06 / 5</u>	<u>4.85 / 5</u>	<u>5.09 / 5</u>

The table 6 shows that median values are mostly 5, indicating no strong preference for a specific facility and a generally balanced demand across all options. Project display areas received the highest mean score (5.09), with business users rating it the highest (mean: 5.25, median: 5.5), reflecting their need for spaces to showcase work. Open workspaces were also rated relatively high, particularly by creators (5.27) and business users (5.13), suggesting a stronger interest in collaborative environments.

Additional facility requirements:

Feedback from open-ended questions provided additional insights into facility requirements. Business users highlighted the need for more collaborative spaces, such as open workshop areas

for experimentation and spaces to showcase LAUDS projects to the community and potential funders. They also emphasised the importance of exchanging ideas with multidisciplinary experts, particularly in areas such as microcontroller programming and electronics. Additional requests included a photo studio for project documentation, testing spaces equipped with immersive technologies (e.g., VR, AR), and small storage areas for project materials. Creators expressed a desire for community gathering spaces, including terraces and libraries, as well as a designated contact person to provide practical help and guidance during project development. Other users did not provide significant additional feedback, indicating that their preferences align more closely with the facilities already outlined.

3.3.4 Findings on digital communication and collaboration tools

To evaluate user preferences for digital communication and collaboration tools, respondents rated how often they expect to use these tools on a scale from 1 (never) to 6 (very frequently).

Table 7 Digital communication and collaboration tool preferences by user type [mean average / median values]

User type	Instant messaging platforms	Video conferencing tools	File sharing and collaboration tools	Tool and equipment management platforms	Version control and code collaboration tools
Business	4.81 / 5	4.69 / 5	5.25 / 5.5	4.19 / 4	4.06 / 4
Creator	4.82 / 5	4.55 / 4	4.82 / 5	3.91 / 4	3.55 / 4
Others	4.29 / 4	4.86 / 5	5.00 / 6	4.29 / 5	4.00 / 4
All	<u>4.71 / 5</u>	<u>4.68 / 5</u>	<u>5.06 / 5</u>	<u>4.12 / 4</u>	<u>3.88 / 4</u>

Overall, all users show a higher demand for file sharing and collaboration tools, with the highest mean (5.06) and median (5) among all tools, and business users rating them the highest (mean: 5.25, median: 5.5), highlighting their strong reliance on these platforms. In contrast, version control and code collaboration tools have the lowest demand, with a mean of 3.88 and a median of 4, indicating their limited relevance for most users. Compared to other groups, creators showed lower demand for both tool and equipment management platforms (mean: 3.91, median: 4) and version control and code collaboration tools (mean: 3.55, median: 4), suggesting these tools are less frequently used in their workflows.

Additional digital communication and collaboration tools:

Feedback from open-ended questions provided further insights into specific needs for digital communication and collaboration tools. Business users requested the inclusion of familiar platforms such as Signal, Telegram, and WhatsApp to facilitate real-time communication. Creators emphasised the importance of open-source platforms and highlighted tools like WhatsApp and interactive boards, such as Miro, for effectively sharing concepts and ideas remotely. Respondents in the "others" group did not provide significant additional feedback, suggesting that their preferences align more closely with the tools already included in the evaluation.

3.3.5 Findings on environmental sustainability measures survey

To assess the importance that the target groups place on environmental sustainability measures, respondents were asked to rate their level of agreement on the importance of environmental sustainability when choosing to use a LAUDS Factory, on a scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 6 (Strongly Agree).

Table 8 Importance of environmental sustainability by user type [mean average / median values]

User type	The importance of environmental sustainability to the user.
Business	5.75 / 6
Creator	6 / 6
Others	5.71 / 6
All	<u>5.82 / 6</u>

From the table 8 above, we can see that the emphasis on environmental sustainability does not differ significantly among different user groups, as all agree that environmental sustainability is important when choosing to use a LAUDS Factory.

To further understand user preferences for different sustainability measures, respondents were asked to rank various environmental sustainability measures in order of importance, from most to least important. For analysis, these rankings were converted into a scoring system, with the highest-ranked measure receiving 5 points and the lowest-ranked receiving 1 point. The table below presents the average ranking scores of each measure across different user groups.

Table 9 shows that the use of environmentally friendly materials is the highest-rated sustainability measure, with business users (4.1 / 4) and creators (4.5 / 4) prioritizing it the most. Waste management and recycling systems ranked slightly lower, and received the highest ratings from the others group (4.1 / 4). Energy and water efficiency received moderate ratings across all groups (3.4 to 3.6 / 3), indicating some importance but not a primary concern. In contrast, environmental certifications and labels received the lowest ratings (1.8 to 2.6 / 2), along with "Other" sustainability measures (1.3 to 1.5 / 1), reflecting that while a few respondents considered additional options, the majority did not prioritize sustainability measures beyond those listed.

Table 9 Ranking of environmental sustainability measures by user type [mean average / median values]

User type	Energy and water efficiency	Use of environmentally friendly materials	Waste management and recycling systems	Environmental certifications and labels	Other
Business	3.6 / 3.5	4.1 / 4	3.6 / 3.5	2.5 / 2	1.3 / 1
Creator	3.5 / 3	4.5 / 4	3.8 / 4	1.8 / 2	1.5 / 1
Others	3.4 / 3	3.6 / 4	4.1 / 4	2.6 / 2	1.3 / 1

Additional sustainability actions suggested by users:

Users provided additional suggestions for sustainability actions to enhance practices within the LAUDS Factory. Business users emphasised the importance of minimising resource usage and increasing awareness of circular design principles to promote sustainable operations. Creators proposed a broader range of ideas, including organising awareness workshops to deepen understanding of sustainable practices, reusing old equipment instead of purchasing new items, and reducing the need for long-distance travel to minimise environmental impact. Respondents in the "others" group did not offer additional feedback on sustainability measures.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable investigates the digital and physical infrastructure categories, requirements and targets necessary to transform LAUDS factories into facilitators for prototyping of distributed and sustainable manufacturing processes by business users and creatives/artists.

The conducted analysis builds upon the outcomes of co-creation workshops conducted in WP1 (see D1.1 "Results and lessons learnt of co-creative workshops") and a targeted survey involving 34 open call applicants. Moreover, the study incorporates contextual inputs on anticipated technical requirements to address the user needs from the four LAUDS factory partners: Université de Lorraine (UL), Fab City Hamburg (FCHH), Taller para la Materialización y el Desarrollo de (grandes) Conceptos (TMDC), and Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (BUW). The quality function deployment methodology is applied to translate user needs into quantifiable technical specifications. The resulting technical requirements and their corresponding target values are presented through circular diagrams and mind maps to identify key priorities and potential technical gaps.

The survey findings reveal both differences and commonalities between the two main target groups of business users and creators. Business users prioritise project development and business-oriented activities, whereas creators focus more on hands-on training and technical collaboration. Both groups place importance on sustainability and highlight the need for core digital infrastructure, such as file-sharing platforms and booking systems. The survey also helped assess the relative importance of various infrastructure needs from the users' perspective, providing weighted input for prioritising the technical requirements.

The QFD analysis identifies several technical gaps in the current infrastructure. While tools such as CNC machines, 3D printers, and laser cutters are widely available, their performance limitations reduce their applicability for complex or large-scale production. Additionally, the absence of plastic recycling systems and electronic prototyping tools constrains material reuse and limits opportunities for hardware innovation. On the digital side, the lack of integrated prototyping software, learning platforms, and collaboration tools poses challenges for design iteration and inter-organizational coordination.

Although this study presents an initial roadmap for infrastructure transformation, several limitations should be acknowledged. The four LAUDS factory partners vary in their characteristics and stages of development, resulting in diverse technical needs. An appropriate infrastructure framework for the LAUDS Factory model (in T2.2) will therefore require further localisation and adaptation during implementation (linked to T3.4). Moreover, the LAUDS factory model remains in

an early phase, and the limited survey sample from the LAUDS Exploration open call #1 may not fully reflect the diversity of potential target users. Some needs identified through the QFD process may also depend on soft support measures such as educational programs, expert guidance, or co-creation workshops. While these elements fall outside the scope of this report, they are nonetheless crucial to the model's overall success. While infrastructure capacity is expected to grow progressively with increasing user demand and prototyping activities, several shared priorities may be addressed in the early stages to support a steep learning curve and long-term usability. For example, integrating material management, resource tracking/monitoring and reuse systems from the outset can contribute to environmental sustainability. Similarly, real-time communication and file-sharing platforms are essential to enable effective collaboration.

Going forward, each site is expected to refine its infrastructure and operations based on existing and potential user feedback, regional conditions, industry/creative/arts focus and, particularly, available resources constraints. Broader stakeholder involvement, specifically from user communities and local decision-makers, will also be essential to gain traction. The QFD methodology, as demonstrated in this report, offers a systematic approach for setting critical requirements and targets. During the analysis process, each LAUDS partner assessed its own technical requirements and target values based on their unique challenges in different directions, which allowed the deriving of cumulative categories for different directions of technical improvements.

In more advanced settings the gap between existing and desired capabilities were distinguished, although this should be analysed further based on the overall LAUDS framework to be settled. These assessments could provide insights into site-specific readiness levels and can serve as a reference for further infrastructure planning as part of WP2 work on analyses of varying scale (T2.2). Moreover, strengthening infrastructure integrity and fostering long-term user engagement will be essential to ensuring that LAUDS factories evolve into resilient, inclusive, sustainable, and culturally embedded models for urban manufacturing.

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Appendices

A Quality function deployment methodology

This appendix introduces the basics of the QFD methodology and how it was applied for this research. Quality Function Deployment (QFD) is a customer-centric and systematic methodology that supports the development, design, and implementation of new products or services. Its primary objective is to translate customer needs and expectations into specific design specifications and technical requirements, integrating these systematically throughout the product development process. Ultimately, QFD helps organisations deliver high-quality products and services as part of multi-generational developments that effectively meet customer demands.

The QFD method has been widely applied across industries such as automotive, shipbuilding, electronics, aerospace, and software. By aligning customer needs with technical solutions, it enables organisations to optimise product development and maintain a competitive edge in dynamic markets.

Developed in the late 1960s by Yoji Akao and Shigeru Mizuno at the Tokyo Institute of Technology, QFD was first applied at Mitsubishi Heavy Industries' Kobe Shipyard to optimise oil tanker design, achieving notable cost reductions. In 1984, Xerox introduced QFD to the United States, marking a significant milestone in its global dissemination. Two years later, Glenn Mazur founded the QFD Institute, accelerating its international adoption. Today, QFD continues to evolve, supported by various national institutes worldwide

Fundamental concepts and tools of QFD

At the core of QFD is the *voice of the customer*, which captures both explicit and implicit customer requirements. These inputs are gathered through various methods, including interviews, surveys, focus groups, warranty data analysis, and field observations. The collected data is systematically organised into a product planning matrix, commonly known as the *house of quality*. In this study, it means that the voice of businesses and creators are considered from the outset.

The house of quality (HoQ) (Figure 5) is a structured and visual tool that converts customer needs into actionable technical requirements, helping teams align customer expectations with product design and development. It includes the following key elements:

- "What" (user needs): Captures explicit and implicit user requirements, forming the foundation of the QFD process.
- "How" (design requirements): Defines the technical solutions to address the identified

needs.

- Correlation matrix: Highlights interactions among technical solutions “how”, identifying synergies or conflicts.
- Degree of correlation: Evaluates the strength of connections between customer needs (“What”) and technical solutions (“How”).
- “How much” (targets): Sets measurable goals for technical solutions to meet user expectations.
- “Why” (improvement): Identifies areas for improvement to enhance user satisfaction

Figure 5 House of quality

The four phases of QFD

The full QFD process (see Figure 6) comprises four key phases, with the first being represented by the House of Quality (HoQ):

1. Product planning
2. Product design
3. Process planning
4. Process control

These four interconnected phases form structured vested matrices that systematically link customer needs to ensuing technical requirements. They ensure alignment and continuity throughout the entire process, with each phase building on the outcomes of the previous one. This structured approach enables manufacturers to determine which features or characteristics should be prioritised in their products and services to maximise customer value. This report specifically focuses on the first phase, product planning, which utilises the initial HoQ to map the digital and physical technical factors required for transformation.

Figure 6 The four phases of QFD

Analytical framework and steps

At this stage of the project, a partial implementation of the QFD process was adopted due to the preliminary refinement phase of the LAUDS Factories model. A full QFD process, which typically involves iterative refinement and comprehensive evaluation of requirement fulfilment (why), is not yet feasible. Instead, the analytical focus is on establishing a foundation for future evaluations by identifying user needs and technical requirements, analysing gaps between current capabilities

and desired target values, and prioritising technical requirements based on their significance and identified gaps. The analysis is structured around the QFD concepts of what, how, and how much, as outlined in the following steps:

1. What – identification of core user needs: The first step aims to answer the question, "What does an ideal LAUDS Factory need to include?" Core user needs were identified based on the analysis presented in the D1.1 report, which synthesised findings from a survey of 34 open call applicants. These user needs reflect stakeholders' expectations and priorities. To ensure clarity and alignment with technical requirements, the needs were systematically categorised and organised. This provides a structured foundation for linking user needs to specific technical requirements in subsequent steps.
2. How – definition of technical requirements: Building on the identified user needs, the next step involved addressing the question, "what technical infrastructure is required to meet these needs?" To answer this, input was collected from four project partners (UL, FCHH, TMDC and BUW) using a structured House of Quality (HoQ) template, as shown in Figure 7. This template ensured consistency in capturing technical requirements and their corresponding target values. The collected inputs were further categorised into two main types: physical infrastructure requirements and digital infrastructure requirements. The relationships between user needs and technical requirements were visualised through a circular link diagram (Figure 1). This diagram illustrates the degree to which each technical requirement fulfilled user needs, represented by the thickness of the connecting lines. Additionally, the importance of each technical requirement was assessed based on the frequency with which it was mentioned by project partners.
3. How much – determination of technical target values: After defining the technical requirements, the third step addresses the question, "how much is needed to meet the requirements?" Target values for each technical requirement were consolidated based on input from the four project partners. These target values were categorised into existing facilities and desired facilities, providing a development measure from the current capabilities of each lab. Additionally, a target value was established for each requirement to serve as a benchmark and guide for future development efforts.
4. Gap analysis: The current and desired states of technical requirements were analysed using two mind maps, while also highlighting unmet needs: the physical infrastructure mind map (Figure 2), which illustrates the relationships between physical infrastructure requirements and their target for improvement, and the digital infrastructure mind map (Figure 3), which visualises the existing and desired capabilities of digital infrastructure.

5. Prioritisation of technical requirements: Based on the gap analysis, technical requirements were prioritised based on their ability to fulfil user needs, which was evaluated based on fulfilment strength and the frequency of mentions. The detailed results of this prioritisation are presented in Section 2: Results.

Technical requirements (product) →				Physical infrastructure														
User needs ↓	Importance of user need of businesses	Importance of user need of creators	Average															
Individual user needs																		
Easy-to-use digital machine tools with sufficient variety for prototyping	4	4	4															
Sufficient capacity of workstations	4	4	4															
Functional areas for prototyping, co-creation, and social interaction	4	4	4															
Seamless system and responsible staff for managing materials inventory	4	4	4															
Easy-to-use digital machine tools for recycling and upcycling of materials	4	4	4															
Easy-to-use digital prototyping tools that connect to manufacturing equipment, enabling seamless transition from design to production	4	4	4															
Easy-to-use groupware platforms for asynchronous collaboration and distributed networks	4	3	4															
Instant messaging tool for quick communication and sharing ideas across the LAUDS network	4	4	4															
An efficient daily operation system, including membership, booking systems, and production management	3	3	3															
Inclusive trainings, tools and resources for supporting education in machine usage and development on different skill levels	4	5	5															
A diverse expert pool covering a variety of professional areas	4	5	5															
Accessible consultancy services for product development assistance	4	4	4															
Professional support for product commercialization, business model development, and marketing	4	3	4															
Established funding mechanisms to support project development and growth of member projects	4	3	4															
Technical indicators with target values →																		
Current situation (Existing or Desired) →																		

Figure 7 The HoQ template

B Survey questions for data acquisition

Fields marked with * are mandatory

Basic Information

* 1. Your gender

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

* 2. What is your age range?

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65 and above

* 3. Which country are you currently located in?

* 4. What is your user type? (Select all that apply)

- Start-up - Owner
- Start-up - Employee
- SME (Small and Medium-sized Enterprise) - Owner
- SME (Small and Medium-sized Enterprise) - Employee
- Artist
- Student
- Researcher
- Freelancer
- Educator/teacher
- Engineer
- Designer
- Corporate Employee
- Other

* 5. Have you ever used a makerspace / fab lab before?

- Yes
- No

* 7. For your projects, how often do you anticipate using the LAUDS Factory each week in the future?

- Less than once a week
- 1-2 times per week
- 3 times or more per week
- 5 times or more per week

Facilitation Activities

8. To what extent do you agree that the following LAUDS Factory activities would be helpful for you?

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 6 = Strongly Agree)

	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Slightly disagree	4 Slightly agree	5 Agree	6 Strongly agree
* LAUDS Factory introduction event	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Technical training (tool and equipment usage training)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Business model development seminars	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Workshops and creative activities (creative discussions, design exchanges, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Guided collaborative project development activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. Do you have any suggestions for the activities listed above or any additional activities that would better meet your needs?

Prototyping Infrastructure

10. Please rate the possibility of your future frequency of using these facilities in the LAUDS Factory

(1 = Never, 6 = Very Frequently)

	1 Never	2 Very Rarely	3 Rarely	4 Occasionally	5 Frequently	6 Very Frequently
* 3D Printer	<input type="radio"/>					
* Laser Cutter	<input type="radio"/>					
* CNC Machine	<input type="radio"/>					
* Welding Equipment	<input type="radio"/>					
* Electronics Workstation (Arduino, Raspberry Pi, VR equipment, etc.) - Please specify briefly which tools in the next question	<input type="radio"/>					
* Woodworking Tools - Please specify briefly which tools in the next question	<input type="radio"/>					

11. Which other equipment do you need to use when working on your projects? Please specify briefly their purpose and frequency of use.

Collaboration Community Facilities

12. To what extent do you agree that the following facilities are important for the development of your projects and collaboration in the LAUDS Factory?

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 6 = Strongly Agree)

	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Slightly Disagree	4 Slightly Agree	5 Agree	6 Strongly Agree
* Meeting/Brainstorming Room – An enclosed room for team meetings and group discussions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Open Workspace – A shared, laptop-friendly space for individual or group computer work.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Coffee Area – A space for coffee and snacks.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Event Space – A area for hosting workshops, lectures, social, or other events.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Project Display Area – A space to showcase completed projects, prototypes, and lessons from failed designs.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. Besides the spaces mentioned above, are there any other facilities you would need in the LAUDS Factory? Please briefly explain their purpose.

14. Please rate how often you expect to use the following digital communication and collaboration tools in the future

(1 = Never, 6 = Very Frequently)

	1 Never	2 Very Rarely	3 Rarely	4 Occasionally	5 Frequently	6 Very Frequently
* Instant Messaging Platforms (e.g., Discord, Slack, Mattermost, etc.) - Facilitates quick communication within teams.	<input type="radio"/>					
* Video Conferencing Tools (e.g., MS Teams, Zoom, etc.) - Enables remote meetings and face-to-face collaboration.	<input type="radio"/>					
* File Sharing and Collaboration Tools (e.g., NextCloud, OneDrive, etc.) - Allows for easy sharing and collaboration on documents and files.	<input type="radio"/>					
* Tool and Equipment Management Platforms (e.g., Fab Manager, FabMan, etc.) - Helps manage the use of tools and resources in a makerspace.	<input type="radio"/>					
* Version Control and Code Collaboration Tools (e.g., GitHub, GitLab, etc.) - Facilitates collaboration on code and version control.	<input type="radio"/>					

15. Are there any other digital communication and collaboration tools that would be beneficial for your project in the LAUDS Factory? Please briefly explain their purpose.

Sustainability Measures

* 16. To what extent do you agree that environmental sustainability is important when choosing to use a LAUDS Factory?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Slightly Disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

* 17. Please rank the following environmental sustainability measures in order of importance when choosing a makerspace, with the topmost being the most important and the bottommost being the least important.

Use drag&drop or the up/down buttons to change the order or accept the initial order.

:: ↑ ↓ Use of environmentally-friendly materials

:: ↑ ↓ Energy and water efficiency

:: ↑ ↓ Waste management and recycling systems

:: ↑ ↓ Environmental certifications and labels

:: ↑ ↓ Other (please specify in the next question if applicable; otherwise, place this option last)

18. Please specify "Other" Measures

C Responses to open-ended survey questions

(Numbering corresponds to the survey questions.)

9. Do you have any suggestions for the activities listed above or any additional activities that would better meet your needs?

Business Users:

- "Presentations of local creators."
- "Visits of other LAUDS factories."
- "I would very much like to receive support and competence in specific areas such as electronics, manufacturing, welding, etc."

- "Every networking event would be great. It is very powerful when you can connect with people who share similar objectives or projects. It would also be enriching to connect between projects that are aligned in their objectives and developments, even if they were not selected in the call."
- "Like every project to have a tutor, but I think this is already solved!"
- "Times for exchange and sharing among different projects."
- "A matching platform (which lasts even after the LAUDS project) for creators and FabLabs."
- "I believe that established facilities/tools to share and discuss project ideas would be beneficial to people involved."

Creator Users:

- "Activities related to innovation, robotics, AI, and the circular economy."
- "How to collaborate with other members or how to build a strong network of providers and partners."
- "Receiving individual sparring would be nice."
- "Events and technical training led by women and non-binary people."
- "One of my team members could give a talk or workshop on AI."
- "I could give a talk on biomimicry, biomorphic design, the LAUDS project concept/process/expected results, the potential obstacles (pains), and potential to solve a real-world problem (gains)."
- "Specific training on plastic recycling tools and equipment."

Other Users:

- "I consider the introduction event as a must-have, as the concept is not widely known."
- "Technical training is important to allow the potential users to become more autonomous, which is a core value for LAUDS. Workshops and creative activities are also important to improve collaboration."
- "Talks about the experiences of other artists, artisans, engineers, etc., that generate a point of discussion among the different people who attend."
- "Expert support for certain technical dilemmas."

11. Which other equipment do you need to use when working on your projects? Please specify briefly their purpose and frequency of use.

Business Users:

- "Press (from FabLab Nancy) to make recycled plastic plates for shells and protective housings."
- "3D printers, robotic arms, CNC."

- “Hot Press: this is used to conglomerate de bio-based boards. It is used very often, is indispensable for the creation of the boards. Also, Mixer: to mix raw material with vegetal glue. Stove: glue fabrication.”
- “3D printing and common tools for working with ceramic materials (e.g., cutters, drills, etc.).”
- “Various hand tools and computer.”

Creator Users:

- “Electronic boards.”
- “Woodworking bench and clamping devices. Daily use.”
- “Workbench.”
- “Angle grinder to cut steel bars and tubes. Frequently use.”
- “It would be great to have access to a CNC/welding station for bigger builds, as I normally gain access to these machines at local makerspaces or artist workshops.”
- “Sewing and stitching machine for textile projects, tools and materials for different printing processes (silk screen, etching, linocut), and a big mechanical printing press.”

Other Users

No feedback was provided.

13. Besides the spaces mentioned above, are there any other facilities you would need in the LAUDS Factory? Please briefly explain their purpose.

Business Users:

- “Open workshop type experimentation space”: A space where creators can meet and experiment together with tools and machines.
- “An exhibition space”: To highlight the projects carried out within LAUDS and so be able to demonstrate to communities and funders.
- “Since we’re working on a multi-disciplinary project, and although we intend to develop almost all aspects ourselves, it would be interesting to be able to exchange ideas with experts in various fields (microPC programming, electricity and electronics, etc.) to improve our approach and open up to new ideas. In the end, when you dig deep enough, you’ll quickly come across the right people, but it’s also possible that you’ll miss out on people who are open to sharing, competent and motivated...”
- “Photo studio with equipment for documentary purposes.”
- “Spaces for testing and the possibility to connect remotely with XR tools.”
- “A little corner for storage. But no extensive storage facilities needed.”

Creator Users:

- “Community gathering spaces. Like a nice terrace.”

- "Library."
- "One person that is my reference contact to reach out to for assistance, practical help, etc."

Other Users

No feedback was provided.

15. Are there any other digital communication and collaboration tools that would be beneficial for your project in the LAUDS Factory? Please briefly explain their purpose.

Business Users:

- "Signal, Telegram, WhatsApp."

Creator Users:

- "Open source platforms please :)"
- "WhatsApp group."
- "I use interactive boards such as Miro to share concepts and ideas remotely."

Other Users

No feedback was provided.

18. Please specify "Other" Measures. (Sustainability regard)

Business Users:

- "First, I'll put the final object of the makerspace usage. It's all about what you want to achieve."
- "Reduction of any usage if possible."
- "Awareness for Circular Design principles."

Creator Users:

- "Awareness workshops."
- "Avoid traveling long distances."
- "Re-use of old equipment, not buying everything new."
- "Passive functionalities (read, that don't require energy)."
- "Organise events to raise awareness on sustainability."

Other Users

No feedback was provided.

D Box Plot Analysis of Survey Data

8. To what extent do you agree that the following LAUDS Factory activities would be helpful for you?
 (1 = Strongly Disagree, 6 = Strongly Agree)

10. Please rate the possibility of your future frequency of using these facilities in the LAUDS Factory (1 = Never, 6 = Very Frequently)

12. To what extent do you agree that the following facilities are important for the development of your projects and collaboration in the LAUDS Factory? (1 = Strongly Disagree, 6 = Strongly Agree)

14. Please rate how often you expect to use the following digital communication and collaboration tools in the future (1 = Never, 6 = Very Frequently)

16. To what extent do you agree that environmental sustainability is important when choosing to use a LAUDS Factory? (1 = Strongly Disagree, 6 = Strongly Agree)

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